

SHOCK FOCUSING IN WATER IN A CONVERGENT CARBON FIBER COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

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1 General Introduction

Underwater explosion (UNDEX) is an energetic event that can yield severe destruction to close-by naval structures. Since a great portion of the energy released by UNDEX is associated with the resulting shock wave in water, the interaction between the shock wave and the solid structure, and following events, such as the bubble formation and collapse etc., are the main reasons for damage caused to the structure. Therefore, laboratory experiments and numerical simulations are designed and conducted to understand the detailed dynamics of such events.

Here, we study the effect of UNDEX on water-filled convergent structures, made of either metal or carbon fiber. Shock focusing in water occurring in convergent structures can lead to extremely high pressures, on the order of GPa. By utilizing converging the shock waves to generate dynamic loading conditions, material properties will be examined under extreme conditions.

Previous studies on UNDEX interaction with solids have mainly focused on direct shock wave impact onto monolithic solid plates immersed in water [1], and optimized sandwich panels [2], etc. However, when structures of more complex geometry, especially convergent shapes, are under shock loading, shock focusing will likely occur. Given such a scenario, the shock strength will increase during the focusing phase. Thus, the dynamics of the fluid structure interaction will be altered as compared with the direct planar impact tests. The time of interaction between shock wave and surrounding structure is typically longer during shock focusing events than for planar impacts.

In this work, both experiments and numerical simulations are designed and carried out for

convergent carbon fiber structures filled with water. To compare the dynamic response of the carbon fiber composite samples, isotropic steel samples having the same thickness as the carbon fiber composites are also investigated. Since the shape of the shock front far enough away from an UNDEX event can be approximated to be planar, all experiments and simulations in this paper starts with a planar incident shock wave.

2 Experiments

Impact experiments were performed using a single-stage gas gun. A projectile launched from the gas gun impacts onto the sample and generates a shock wave in the water-filled convergent section. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2, with a top view of the gas gun, the sample placement and the Z-folded visualization system.

The shock wave propagation, the fluid-structure interaction and the dynamic response of the surrounding structure are studied using high-speed photography visualizations and strain gauge measurements.

2.1 Experimental Sample

The geometry of the sample is designed to have the ability to focus the shock wave to the focal point with minimum losses [3-5]. The shape is called a logarithmic spiral and is depicted in Figure 1. The necessary equations to derive the shape for a logarithmic spiral with water as the shock medium using the Mie-Grüneisen equation of state is derived in reference [7].

The carbon fiber sample is 5.8 mm in thickness, and made of four laminates with four layers in each

laminate. The layers are stacked using a combination of 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, and 90° ply angles. Steel samples were made of type 304 steel with the same thickness as the carbon fiber composite sample.

2.2 Experimental Setup

To generate the shock wave in water, a gas gun is utilized. The gun barrel is connected to a pressure chamber filled with compressed air. The projectile, which is a 57 mm long cylinder with 50 mm diameter made out of PTFE-filled Delrin, is launched by the pressurized air and impacts onto the sample at the exit of the gun barrel. Through a direct impact from the projectile, a planar shock wave is generated in the test sample. Once the shock wave enters the region of interest, a visualization technique called schlieren optics [6] is used to unveil the change of refraction index, or equivalently the density and pressure change, in the water. The test sample, Fig. 1, is mounted between two 12 mm thick optical quality polycarbonate windows (only one is shown in Fig. 1). A polycarbonate piston is plugged into the opening of the sample, for the purposes of both sealing the water inside the convergent section and transmitting the shock wave into the water. All the contacts between different parts are carefully sealed using silicone glue or epoxy to prevent water leakage.

The two arrows in Fig. 1 represent the location of the two strain gauges that are used to obtain strain measurements on the convergent structure. The location is the same for both the carbon fiber composite and the steel sample. Wang and Eliasson further describe the experimental system in reference [7].

2.3 Experimental Results

A series of schlieren images are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. The water-filled region and the piston are denoted by (a) and (b) in the first frame of Fig. 3. This frame is taken before the test as a reference picture. The rest of the frames are taken 6.9 microseconds apart. The shock wave location is marked with a white arrow in the subsequent images. As can be seen from the images, the shock wave is planar and this indicates a planar impact.

The second white arrows in the fifth and sixth frames in Fig. 3 point at locations where cavitation occurs.

The formation of the cavitation bubbles is due to the propagation of the stress waves in the carbon fibers to the tip region [8]. The stress waves in the fibers travel with a speed three times faster than the shock wave in the water region. Analysis of the motion of the water-solid interface shows an initial contraction followed by an expansion. The expansion causes a lower pressure at the region of convergence and the region of lower pressure is transmitted backward towards the undisturbed region ahead of the shock wave in the water, by comparing frames five, six and seven in Fig. 3.

A photo taken of the side of the composite fiber structure after the experiment has been performed is shown in Fig. 5. The arrow points at a region with visible damage due to delamination, and it is very close to the focal region where the extremely high pressures occur.

A series of schlieren images obtained from the steel sample are shown in Fig. 6. The time interval between the frames is 6.3 microseconds. As can be seen, the wave propagation pattern obtained in this series is qualitatively different from the wave pattern observed for the carbon fiber composite sample (Fig. 4). The precursor waves, which travel ahead of the main shock in water, are presented along both upper and lower surfaces of the sample. Such feature is formed by the fast-going shear wave inside the steel sample. Whereas the shear wave speed of the composite sample is lower than the shock wave speed in water, thus this type of precursor wave is absent in Fig. 3 and 4.

3 Numerical Simulations

Due to the highly non-linear, transient and coupled nature of the experiments, explicit finite element analysis is chosen to simulate the shock focusing event and the dynamic response of the surrounding structure. The numerical simulations for the current setup are performed with a commercial code (Abaqus/Explicit v6.12) using a Coupled Eulerian Lagrangian (CEL) approach [9]. All the major experimental components, including the projectile,

the piston and the test sample, are modeled with properly assigned solid material properties under Lagrangian formulation. The water domain is meshed using Eulerian grids, and the material property of water is modeled with the Mie-Grüneisen equation of state.

The peak pressure behind a spherical shock wave is decreasing with time and distance away from the source. Thus, the shock front will experience a deceleration, and the Mach number of the shock wave will decay as it expands from the source of the explosion. In this work, we are considering structures close to where UNDEX happens, we chose an initial Mach number of $M = 1.1$ for all the simulations. This Mach number represents a shock wave 3 meters away from a 135-kilogram Trinitrotoluene (TNT) charge.

There is no interlaminar modeling in the current simulations, so any results where delamination is likely to occur have to be inferred from deformation and strain measurements, but cannot be observed directly.

3.1 Numerical Simulation Results

Results from the numerical simulations show that the composite sample undergoes deformation and delamination close to the focal region. Two plots at a time instance 98.2 microseconds after the projectile impact are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. In Fig. 7, the original undeformed structure is shown in grey color and the deformed shape is demonstrated in green color using a magnified deformation scale of eight times. A clear stretching of the inner surface and shrinkage of the outer surface close to the tip region of the composite structure can be observed. Such deformation suggests an internal stress accumulation. By plotting the normal strain component in the horizontal direction, Fig. 8, this behavior can be confirmed. Negative values of the strain shown on the plot indicate a tensile stress, which can initiate interlaminar cracks causing delaminations [10].

The coupling between the fluid and the structure is important since it may influence the dynamic response of the surrounding structure to a high degree. The main factor that determines the fluid-

structure interaction is the impedance, speed of sound times density, of the water and the surrounding material. For larger values of impedance mismatch, the lower the fluid-structure coupling is expected to be.

The pressure field displayed for the water-filled region is plotted using the same scale in both Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 at a time instant 46.4 microseconds after the projectile impacts onto the specimen. As can be seen in Fig. 9, there is a distinct pressure wave pattern showing up in the case of a steel structure. This is also directly comparable with the experimental visualization in Fig. 6. However, when comparing the pressure field in the water for the composite sample, no precursor waves are visible in the simulations, see Fig. 10.

4 Comparison between experiments and simulations

One of the main goals of this investigation is to compare the experimental results with the results from the numerical simulations. The strain signals measured in both carbon fiber composite sample and steel structure experiments are plotted against the strain obtained in the numerical simulations in Fig. 11 and 12.

Figure 11 shows the comparison of results obtained for the carbon fiber composite sample. Time is taken to be zero when the projectile impact happens. In the experiment, the initial rise indicated in the strain measurement at the second gauge is right after the shock enters water. This straining, that occurs before the shock in water has reach the strain gauge location, serves as an indication of the cavitation bubble formation observed in the schlieren images obtained in the high-speed visualizations.

The strain results from the experiment and simulation show the same trend qualitatively, although the magnitude of the strain signal obtained in the experimental results are in general more dampened. This is most likely due to the fact that in the simulations, the sample has no contact constraints where in the experiment the samples are always in contact with the windows and the piston through silicone glue or epoxy, which are applied to prevent water from leaking out. The damping effect of the glue applied at the adjoining interfaces can be

further modeled through varying the magnitude of the stiffness-damping coefficient.

The correlation of the strain measurements from experiments and simulations can be further estimated by calculating the Russell error [11], see Table 1. The strain measurement comparison at gauge 1 indicates acceptable correlation between experiments and simulations ($RC < 0.28$) for both types of materials. However at gauge 2, severe deviation has been shown through Russell error. At this strain gauge location, the shock wave has had time to focus, and effects from glue present in the experiments most likely influence the results. Further investigations are necessary to fully understand the differences observed.

In the experiments, the strain measurements from the steel sample indicate minimum strain amplitude of about -1.7×10^{-3} , while that for the composite sample is around -2.4×10^{-3} . Despite the difference in the amplitude, it takes about 80 microseconds after the projectile impact to reach the minimum strain for both cases. This strongly suggests that the critical time scale remains very similar for different types of materials for the dynamical events following a shock wave impact given that the incident shock strength is the same.

5 Discussion and Conclusions

The overall qualitative behavior of the experiments is well captured by the numerical simulations, even though the quantitative behavior is not captured as well at this stage.

In conclusion, formation of cavitation bubble clouds has been observed in experiments using a convergent carbon fiber structure. The cavitation bubble formation is due to the fast longitudinal wave traveling inside carbon fibers, which is higher than the shock speed in the water-filled region. The mechanism of the delamination around the focal region close to the sample tip is revealed through numerical simulations where the deformation and strain amplitudes can be readily monitored throughout the shock-focusing phase.

Therefore, we conclude that this work has successfully been able to show the potential to use simulations in Abaqus/Explicit combined with the

coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian formulation to realistically simulate shock-focusing events inside convergent steel or composite structures.

For future work, carbon fiber face sheets will be used to create a three-part sandwich structure with a foam core in the middle. This new structure will be investigated using the shock focusing techniques outlined in this work.

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Fig. 1 Experimental sample: (a) transparent polycarbonate window (b) convergent water-filled sample, and (c) piston to block water from leaking. The arrows indicate the location of the two strain gauges.

Fig. 2 Experimental setup; (1) gas gun, (2) 1.8m long, 50mm diameter gun barrel, (3) velocity sensors, (4) light source, (5) spherical mirror, (6) flat mirror, (7) flat mirror, (8) schlieren edge, (9) lenses, (10) high-speed camera, and (11) experimental specimen. The light beam is shown to illustrate the optical path of the Z-folded schlieren system.

Fig. 3 A series of schlieren images showing the shock wave propagation and the fluid-structure interaction for a fiber composite sample.

Fig. 4 Continuation of the schlieren series shown from Fig. 3. The white arrow denotes the location of the shock wave.

Fig. 5 Photo taken of the experimental sample after experiment showing signs of delamination at the focal region.

Fig. 6 A series of schlieren images showing the shock wave propagation and the fluid-structure interaction for a steel sample.

Fig. 7 Results from the numerical simulations showing deformation in the composite sample. The original undeformed structure is shown in grey color and the deformed shape is shown in green color with a deformation scaling 8 times larger than the original case.

Fig. 8 Results from the numerical simulations showing strain levels in the composite sample. (The contour is showing variation in E11.)

Fig. 9 Results from the numerical simulations showing wave pattern with visible precursor waves in the water-filled region for the steel sample. The grey region is due to the high pressure beyond upper plotting limit.

Fig. 10 Results from the numerical simulations showing wave pattern with no visible precursor waves in the water-filled region for the composite sample. The grey region is due to the high pressure beyond upper plotting limit.

Fig. 11 Comparison of strain signal from gauge one and two for the experimental and numerical results for the carbon fiber composite sample. Dotted lines show simulation results.

Fig. 12 Comparison of strain signal from gauge one and two for the experimental and numerical results for the steel sample. Dotted lines show simulation results.

	Magnitude error	Phase error	Comprehensive error
Gauge1 (steel)	0.15	0.13	0.18
Gauge2 (steel)	0.01	0.72	0.64
Gauge1 (CFC)	0.18	0.11	0.19
Gauge2 (CFC)	0.43	0.49	0.58

Table 1 Russell error.

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